

THE BENEFITS AND CHALLENGES OF CULTURAL DIVERSITY IN EDUCATIONAL SETTING

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Abstract. *People in different cultures need to understand each other in order to live and study together, that need to learn about other cultures. This work analyzes the advantages and challenges of cultural diversity in education.*

Keywords: *Cultural diversity, education, setting, challenges, multiculturalism.*

ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА И ПРОБЛЕМЫ КУЛЬТУРНОГО РАЗНООБРАЗИЯ В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ СРЕДЕ

Аннотация. *Людям разных культур необходимо понимать друг друга, чтобы жить и учиться вместе, им необходимо узнавать о других культурах. В этой работе анализируются преимущества и проблемы культурного разнообразия в образовании.*

Ключевые слова: *культурное разнообразие, образование, постановка, вызовы, мультикультурализм.*

INTRODUCTION

People start to learn everything by learning their culture. For instance, having a concept of what is right or what is wrong. As a culture develops, people begin to compare their home culture with others.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Cultural diversity is always important in our lives, especially in the educational process. Today we meet representatives of different nationalities in different organizations and educational institutions. People, no matter what nationality or culture they should understand and respect each other and live in the same level without any discrimination. Additionally, cultural diversity gives people opportunity to find their own ways with different experience and it can also help people to share experience with other nationalities. Humankind requires acknowledgement from others in order to live with dignity, especially in a society where cultural diversity is a truth rather than a belief. The way individuals perceive a culture and the people linked with it has an impact on how they treat the culture and the people. Cultural diversity has been widely adopted in politics around the world, but it also used in education. To be clear, it helps people to learn how they can work and make decisions together. Language plays an important role in culture. The origin meanings of the culture are reflected in the language, which it uses. Language is vital for a culture's survival since it reflects people's perspectives on the world. The language used to encapsulate many of a culture's core meanings. Furthermore, language is linked to power and examples In many societies, people's ability to communicate in the dominant language, such as Cantonese in Hong Kong, has a significant impact n their social position, sense of belonging, and access to resources.

RESULTS

Multiculturalism, which strives to foster social cohesiveness through an atmosphere where many cultures are recognized has risen in popularity as a result of the increase in cultural diversity.

Frequently, the terms “cultural diverse” and “multiculturalism” are used interchangeably. Dr. Caleb Rosado, a sociologist who specializes in diversity and multiculturalism, outlined seven key steps in the definition of multiculturalism:

- recognizing the rich diversity of civilizations;
- respecting differences;
- recognizing the value of many cultural manifestations and contributions;
- appreciating what other civilizations have to offer;
- inviting diverse groups to contribute;
- motivating individuals to be critical of their own prejudices in order to develop themselves and others to reach their full potential;
- and celebrating rather than tolerating differences in order to promote unity through diversity.

The advantages of diversity in education, particularly higher education, are numerous, benefiting students’ academic and social experiences as well as their future prospects. Students can cooperate with people of different races, nations and cultural backgrounds while also challenging their preconceived views as a result of diversity’s positive effects. People are more aware of, comprehend and tolerate other ideas and practices as a result of this.

Here are top five student benefits of diversity on campus:

1. Cultural diversity on campus enhances the educational experience.

Students have the opportunity to learn from people various origins and upbringing through culturally varied classroom and social interactions, which leads to improved innovation and collaboration.

“Research demonstrates that overall academic and social impacts of more racial diversity on campus are likely to be good, ranging from higher levels of academic achievements to the enhancement of near and long-term intergroup relations” according to the Center for American Progress.

College students today are more varied than ever before, bringing a wide range of experiences, viewpoints, backgrounds, and beliefs to campus. Diversity officers and student affairs professionals must take meaningful initiatives toward inclusive excellence to adapt to shifting population.

2. On campus diversity increases communications and thought-processing abilities. Students are given regular opportunities to contact with people from varied backgrounds on diverse campus, allowing them to learn to communicate more effectively and often in ways that they are not accustomed to.

Students who interacted with racially and ethnically diverse persons demonstrated significant advances in cognitive skills, for example, critical thinking and problem-solving, according to an article from The Century Foundation.

3. Stereotypes are challenged on campus by diversity.

Students are frequently reared in groups with similar financial, racial or cultural backgrounds. Many students, regardless of whether they identify as members of a minority or culturally diverse group, will be confronted with preexisting prejudices or norms that may have developed throughout adolescence. Students can become more accepting, tolerant, and thoughtful members of society if they are given opportunity to critically examine their experiences.

4. Student might identify with their leaders. Students benefit from diversity on campus in more ways than just having culturally different peers. They also get to see and experience different leadership styles from academics, staff, administrators, and members of the community.

For many pupils, it is an opportunity to witness someone from a similar background who they can model themselves after. This has a particularly strong influence on students from historically underrepresented groups. It is vital to ensure that the demographics of representation are compatible with our student body, both existing students and those we intend to enroll, when considering those we hire within our campus communities.

5. Students are better prepared for the workforce when they are exposed to a diverse range of experiences.

“Education in a diverse setting prepares students to become good citizens in an increasingly complex, pluralistic society; it fosters mutual respect and teamwork and, it helps to build communities whose members are judged by the quality of their character and contributions,” according to the American Council on Education.

Finally, research shows that diversity in education, especially on college campuses, improves “intellectual engagement, self-motivation, citizenship and cultural involvement, as well as academic skills like critical thinking, problem-solving and writing for students of all races. Students gain immediately from interacting with varied classmates outside of the classroom, making them better scholars, thinkers and citizens.

DISCUSSION

Here are three theories about challenges of cultural diversity in teaching system:

First one is theory of cultural deficiency. According to this hypothesis, some students struggle in school because their home environment’s linguistic, social, and they are not appropriately prepared for the duties they would be asked to do in school because of their cultural characteristics. Some pupils, for example, are not read as regularly at home as other children, which has a negative impact on their vocabulary development.

2. Theory of expectation. Teachers often have lower expectations of students from various racial, ethnic and cultural backgrounds. Teachers approach teaching in ways that reflect their low expectations when they assume poor performance from their students. Surprisingly, students tend to perform at the low levels that expected by their teachers. Rosenthal and Jacobson explored this notion in their Pygmalion Effect study in 1968. During the school year, a group of teachers were informed that their kids were due for an intellectual development spurt. Despite the fact that the kids’ academic achievement was mediocre, the professors interacted with them based on this expectation. By the end of the year, all children in the experimental group had improved academically and socially.

Third one is Cultural differences. The cultural difference theory emphasizes the importance for teachers to be aware of the difference between the school atmosphere and the home environment. It is based on idea that students raised in different cultural settings may approach education and learn in different ways. People from other cultural traditions may approach education differently than what is taught in American schools. This is a completely different method to learning and one that teachers at an American school with Polynesian children may need to explore. There is a strong reason to look for and acknowledge cultural differences.

CONCLUSIONS

To sum up, this article proved that cultural diversity assists us in recognizing and respecting “ways of being” that are not always our own. As we engage with others, we may build bridges of truth, respect and understanding across cultures. Furthermore, due of its diversity, our country is more interesting to live in. Language skills, new ways of thinking and new viewpoints are all brought by people from various cultures.

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